

Glossary and Observation Prompts for Evaluating a Co-Creation Workshop

Definitions:

1. **Co-Creation:** Co-creation refers to the collaborative approach of creative problem-solving between diverse stakeholders at all project stages. It emphasizes diverse stakeholders at all parts of the initiative process, beginning with determining and defining the problem, through to the final stages of a project (3).
2. **Co-Creation Method:** Co-creation methods encompass a diverse range of tools, activities, approaches, and techniques employed across the entirety of the co-creation process. These methods serve various purposes, including but not limited to recruitment, facilitation, data collection, reflection, data analysis, and dissemination. Notably, these methods can be quantitative, qualitative, participatory, or a blend of these, allowing for flexibility in achieving diverse objectives (4).
3. **Effectiveness:** Effectiveness evaluates how well the intended goals are reflected in the outcomes delivered by the method. Assessing the effectiveness of a specific method (or methods) and concluding is crucial for identifying potential areas for improvement and verifying the realization of intended outcomes. Furthermore, the effectiveness of a method relies on its appropriateness and alignment with a specific context (5,6).
4. **Component:** A component serves as a standard or principle in evaluation, forming the basis for the evaluative judgements to assess effectiveness. The purpose of an evaluation component is to provide consistent prompts for posing pertinent questions during evaluation. Criteria can be considered as lenses through which one can understand and analyze a co-creation process (2,7,8).
 - a. **Process:** Process components encompass a set of standards and rules against which the co-creation method can be evaluated. They are related to the potential acceptance of a procedure and examine how components of the method contribute to the effective involvement of co-creators (6,9,10).
 - b. **Outcome:** Outcome components represent expected results based on standards of practice for a specific co-creation method. The assessment of outcomes directly aligns with the objective of the method (6).

PROSECO Components:

Criterion Name	Type	Definition	Observation Prompt
1. Useful Outputs	outcome	This component evaluates whether the method or process generates outputs that are useful for the co-creators or the process itself. It also evaluates the diverse range of output formats used for visualizing the generated data, acknowledging that different contexts or projects may require distinct formats.	Co-creators described what holds significant value to them. It used a variety of formats for presenting data and information, aiming to fit the co-creators and the setting in a way that allows co-creators to engage.
2. Reliability	outcome	This component evaluates how well a method or process performs its intended function without failure or deviation. A reliable process consistently produces similar results under similar conditions, which are accurate and in accordance with the intended specifications or requirements. It can also assess the ability to ensure consistency of the solutions, data, or information, providing a basis for decision-making and further analyses or iterations.	Co-creators were working with data that was provided iteratively throughout the methods of the workshop, and there was repeated validation of the data accuracy.
3. Clarity	process	This component evaluates the effectiveness in articulating and ensuring a clear understanding of the collaboration process among the co-creators, including the nature and scope of the task.	Co-creators asked clarifying questions for clear communication, swiftly addressing any confusion. They showed understanding through affirmative gestures like nodding and taking notes. Responses to prompts were relevant, indicating comprehension. Body language aligned with instructions, and facilitators adapted approaches for clarity.
4. Transparency	process and outcome	This component evaluates the openness regarding the inputs, outputs, and procedural steps of a method or process. It evaluates how well it ensures clear visibility of its steps, components and how clearly it connects input to outcomes.	The inputs, outputs, and procedural steps were made visible. The facilitator described how the inputs were gathered during the activity, and how they led to the outcome (if there was an intended outcome).

5. Impactful Decision-Making	process and outcome	This component evaluates how well the co-creation method or process facilitates a comprehensive and productive decision-making process. It evaluates whether a decision-making process is structured enough to reach significant, influential or effective results, that is based on agreement among the co-creators.	Co-creators were invited to take part in making a decision. The decision-making process was structured and facilitated a productive decision-making process. The co-creators could discuss their choices and preferences, which were then incorporated into decisions made.
6. Conflict Management	process criterion	This component evaluates the ability to address, manage, and resolve conflicts among competing interests within the group. It assesses how well the method or process not only handles conflicts but also leverages them to stimulate constructive debate and foster further development. The emphasis is on promoting resolution in a manner that cultivates a harmonious environment, sustains group cohesion, and utilizes conflicts as opportunities for growth. It aims to ensure that conflicts are handled constructively, and decisions are reached through consensus, thus promoting a cooperative and positive development process.	Conflicts were handled constructively, with all co-creators and facilitators working towards solutions. They were leveraged to stimulate constructive debate and foster development, promoting resolution for a harmonious environment and group cohesion. Decisions were reached through consensus.
7. Perceptions	process	This component evaluates the subjective viewpoints, interpretations, and insights of the co-creators regarding various aspects of the collaborative process and its outcomes. It explores the individual and collective perspectives, attitudes, and experiences of those actively engaged in co-creation efforts.	The method or activity encouraged open dialogue and the exchange of diverse viewpoints among co-creators. The facilitator treated all co-creators equally, valuing their contributions and perspectives, ensuring genuine representation of all inputs. Additionally, it fostered mutual understanding, bridging differences in language, approach, and viewpoint.
8. Impartial Collaboration	process and outcome	This component places a strong emphasis on conducting the co-creation process independent of outside interference. It evaluates the commitment to maintaining a fair and unbiased environment where collaboration occurs without undue influence or bias	Collaboration thrived in a fair, unbiased environment, prioritizing co-creators' perspectives over external pressures. Co-creators contributed equally, refraining from interruptions, with everyone having opportunities to speak. Co-creators and the facilitators displayed open

		from internal or external pressures. It aims to ensure that the co-creation process remains focused on the co-creators and their perspectives rather than being swayed by other interests or pressures.	and inclusive body language (e.g., facing each other, relaxed posture, smiling and making eye contact, nodding, actively listening, and respecting each other's personal space).
9. Efficiency	process	This component evaluates the overall performance in optimizing time and resources required to produce the desired outcome, while ensuring that the method or process remains impactful and effective in achieving its intended goals. The aim is to streamline the process without compromising effectiveness.	The method efficiently utilized time and resources, with co-creators effectively using materials. Transitions between instructions, implementation, and closure were seamless. Group interactions were well-coordinated, with clear transitions in and out of groups. The method was flexible and avoided redundancy, adapting to changes. Downtime was minimal, ensuring continuous engagement and productivity.
10. User-Friendly Execution	process	This component evaluates the user-friendliness and ease of execution for both the co-creators and the facilitator. It encompasses various considerations, such as the utilization of graphical visualization techniques, metaphors, or plain language, when possible, to enhance co-creators understanding. Additionally, it emphasizes inclusivity by ensuring an intuitive execution that aligns with the diverse needs of all co-creators.	The facilitator used graphic visuals to enhance understanding and emphasized inclusivity by adapting the delivery in a way that aligned with the needs of all co-creators. The facilitator was able to deliver the method with ease. Co-creators engaged in the activity without hesitation and demonstrated that they could complete the task without challenges or obstacles. They showed confident body language, and there were smooth transitions between steps. Co-creators required minimal assistance or guidance.
11. Resource Accessibility	process	This component evaluates the user-friendliness and ease of execution for both the co-creators and the facilitator. It encompasses various considerations, such as the utilization of graphical visualization techniques, metaphors, or plain language, when possible, to enhance co-creators understanding. Additionally, it emphasizes inclusivity by ensuring an intuitive execution that aligns with the diverse needs of all co-creators.	There was an accessible and fair allocation of resources, and co-creators could easily obtain essential resources (e.g., materials, information, digital resources, time, or access to experts). All co-creators had equitable access to vital resources, promoting overall inclusivity and effectiveness.

12. Group Dynamics	process	This component evaluates the ability to foster active engagement, high involvement, and the strategic use of personalized and interactive aspects to create a harmonious and productive co-creation environment. The focus is on how the method or process manages the dynamics of the group (e.g. empathy, discussions, trust building) and encourages respectful interactions and cooperation among co-creators.	Co-creators were highly engaged in numerous interactions, facilitated by personalized and interactive elements strategically incorporated to foster a harmonious and productive environment. The facilitator ensured that interactions among co-creators were effectively managed to encourage positive engagement and collaboration. Tools such as templates, worksheets, or canvases were utilized to facilitate joint task completion, promoting active participation among co-creators. During collaborative tasks, co-creators exhibited welcoming body language, including smiles, laughter, and gestures of support, further enhancing the collaborative atmosphere.
13. Objective Alignment	process and outcome	This component evaluates the effectiveness in aligning with the objectives intended to be achieved. It also assesses how well the method or process supports and aligns with the goals and intentions of those involved. The emphasis is on ensuring that the co-creation process and the outcome align harmoniously with the initially intended objectives, contributing to a meaningful alignment between the method or process and the overarching goals.	The objectives were achieved as intended. It ensured that the methods and their outcome aligned harmoniously with the initially intended objectives, contributing to a meaningful alignment between the method and the objectives. The task was completed as outlined in the framing of the method.
14. Impact Assessment	process and outcome	This component evaluates the impact of the method or process on the co-creators. For example, it assesses whether co-creators have increased their capacity to engage or acquired additional knowledge. It also evaluates how co-creators influence the process, such as whether the outcomes reflect their contributions.	The method was effective in assessing and measuring the impact of participation. It delivered concrete outcomes that reflected the influence of co-creators. It also facilitated the acquisition of knowledge during the co-creation process.
15. Experience	process	This component evaluates the co-creators' holistic experience within the method or process. It includes, for example, their comfort level, their perception of success, or their enjoyment of the process.	The co-creators appeared comfortable, relaxed, and showed signs of enjoyment. The co-creators were willing to engage in the method. The co-creators were attentive

			and maintained eye contact with the facilitator and the other co-creators, or were taking notes.
16. Satisfaction	process and outcome	This component evaluates the level of satisfaction and/or dissatisfaction among the co-creators who participated in the process.	Co-creators expressed satisfaction with the method or were showing visible signs of satisfaction (e.g., smiling or positive facial expressions, open body language such as facing the facilitator or the person that is speaking, keeping arms uncrossed, and maintaining good posture). The co-creators expressed appreciation by clapping, thanking the facilitator, or other co-creators.

References:

1. Hartson HR, Andre TS, Williges RC. Criteria For Evaluating Usability Evaluation Methods. *Int J Human-Computer Interact.* 2003 Feb 1;15(1):145–81. doi:10.1207/S15327590IJHC1501_13
2. OECD. DAC Quality Standards for Development Evaluation [Internet]. OECD Publishing; 2010 [cited 2023 Nov 22]. (DAC Guidelines and Reference Series). Available from: https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/development/dac-quality-standards-for-development-evaluation_9789264083905-en doi:10.1787/9789264083905-en
3. Vargas C, Whelan J, Brimblecombe J, Allender S. Co-creation, co-design, co-production for public health – a perspective on definition and distinctions. *Public Health Res Pract.* 2022;32(2). doi:10.17061/phrp3222211
4. Agnello DM, Balaskas G, Steiner A, Chastin S. Methods Used in Co-Creation Within the Health CASCADE Co-Creation Database and Gray Literature: Systematic Methods Overview. *Interact J Med Res.* 2024 Nov 11;13(1):e59772. doi:10.2196/59772
5. Sillak S, Borch K, Sperling K. Assessing co-creation in strategic planning for urban energy transitions. *Energy Res Soc Sci.* 2021 Apr 1;74:101952. doi:10.1016/j.erss.2021.101952
6. Rowe G, Frewer LJ. Evaluating Public-Participation Exercises: A Research Agenda. *Sci Technol Hum Values.* 2004 Oct;29(4):512–56. doi:10.1177/0162243903259197

7. Blackstock KL, Kelly GJ, Horsey BL. Developing and applying a framework to evaluate participatory research for sustainability. *Ecol Econ*. 2007 Feb 1;60(4):726–42. doi:10.1016/j.ecolecon.2006.05.014
8. Longworth GR, Agnello DM, Chastin S, Davis A, Hidalgo ES, Baselga SV, et al. Evaluating the co-creation process in public health interventions: the PROSECO framework. *Public Health*. 2025 Aug 1;245:105783. doi:10.1016/j.puhe.2025.105783
9. Maskrey S, Priest S, Mount NJ. Towards evaluation criteria in participatory flood risk management. doi:10.1111/jfr3.12462
10. Public Participation Methods: A Framework for Evaluation - Gene Rowe, Lynn J. Frewer, 2000 [Internet]. [cited 2023 Nov 22]. Available from: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/016224390002500101>